
How To Clone Your Friend

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Abstract

We propose an experiment demonstrating an autonomous system's capacity to construct a Triple A quality video game, all in the span of 2 minutes, that's indistinguishable from a human creator.

For this experiment, the autonomous agent ports digital clones of real people into a simulation, where their digital counterparts compete against each other in a battle-royal style 100-player game. The autonomous agent creates the game, by mimicking a human's game design process - where it traverses the Unreal Editor for Fortnite (Game Engine), to create the game's initial codebase, while simultaneously relying on other models for help with the storytelling and asset generation process. This approach is heavily inspired by the work over at Minion AI.

For an Autonomous AI Agent to complete complex tasks, we propose a new system architecture leveraging a single Multi-Modal Super LLM (S-Model), a potentially infinite number of Coordinator LLM's (C-Models), and a potentially infinite number of Expert Models (E-Models)

This architecture is an update to The Sparsely-Gated Mixture-of-Experts (MoE) approach from Noam Shazeer and the Google Brain Team. The updated architecture is called the Modular Expert Workflow System (MEW). The underpinning of MEW is that long chains of expert models, managed in groups by Coordinator LLM's, reporting to a single multi-modal model, perform best. A master chef running a Michelin star restaurant might manage 10 top-tier sous-chefs, who in turn each direct a team of 5 line-cooks. Each sous-chef is an expert in their culinary niche, and together this group is more capable than any one master chef would ever be.

1. Introduction

The current state of machine learning still requires a human in the loop for completing the most complex tasks. Take creating a movie – today’s models can help with the video generation, storyline development, editing, character design, dialogue, soundtrack composition, subtitle translation, special effects, and much more. One by one, the industry has developed narrow models, to aid or replace the human in the movie creation process. But, to produce a great film, these models can’t work in isolation, they must be unified, and for the time being, the models must be coordinated by a human that understands the overarching objective and storyline.

As the next step in humanity’s quest for “the singularity”, there needs to be an architecture that helps autonomous agents coordinate large troves of sub-models within a single parallel process - to create movies, build mobile apps, run companies, and of course generate video games.

Open-source packages such as Auto-GPT and LangChain have hinted at the early stages of autonomous agent construction, but there hasn’t been a reimagination at the architecture layer for solving the most complex of tasks – so the Modular Expert Workflow System (MEW) is born.

Research on BDI Agents, Swarm Intelligence, and Finite State Machines, have little by little pulled us in the direction of understanding the underlying components of metacognition – a fundamental concept for constructing agent intelligence. But until the recent advances surrounding multi-modal LLM’s that can interact with, and direct feed-forward sub-networks, the resources haven’t been available to formulate a novel approach to agent construction.

The study of (Belief-Desire-Intention) Agents, and precisely the analysis of the theoretical underpinning of these agents was paramount in crafting our initial structure for MEW:

$$\Psi(B, D, I, S) = \int^M (\alpha \cdot \nabla B(t) + \beta \cdot \Gamma(D(t)) + \gamma \cdot \Lambda(I(t), S(t)) + \delta \cdot F(B(t), D(t), I(t))) dt$$

The equation delineates a sophisticated conceptual framework for BDI agent systems, where it encapsulates the dynamism inherent in a metacognitive process. It postulates a continuous-time, integrative function that captures the nuanced interplay between an agent's evolving beliefs, desires, and intentions—core components of BDI theory—and their emergent behaviors influenced by swarm intelligence principles. This interaction is moderated through a complex feed-forward network structure, analogous to the operational intricacies of multi-modal Large Language Models (LLMs). The mathematical representation underscores the importance of temporal adaptation in agent cognition, reflecting state-of-the-art research in adaptive algorithms and autonomous systems. It implicitly acknowledges the necessity for BDI agents to harmonize internal cognitive states with external, collective intelligence, thereby propelling forward the understanding of agent-based systems and their potential to mimic sophisticated, real-world decision-making processes.

As Grace Hopper said when she released COBOL in 1960, “For the first time, we have made the rocks talk.” Through MEW, maybe we can now convince the rocks to build games for us too.

2. Experiment

For the proposed simulation experiment, the battle-royale style gameplay inspiration stems from Koushun Takami's 1996 Novel, and in more recent times – the likes of Squid Game, The Hunger Games, and clearly Fortnite. On November 5, 2023, Fortnite had 44.7 million DAU, which is indicative of the popularity that comes with the battle-royale style game mechanic.

The proposed simulation relies on open-source base models. The open-source machine learning ecosystem is exceptionally dynamic and robust, contradicting the outdated view held by some of the twitter 'experts' who claim it lags behind by two years.

Even though the simulation is in the style of Fortnite, the reward mechanic is not in obtaining a “victory royale”. Instead, the gameplay 1) ports 100 digitally cloned people via a Playwright scrapping job that pulls their personality from tweet data, voice from YouTube, and appearance from Google Images into the simulation. 2) The 100 people awake inside a hacker house as startup founders. 3) The startup founder that is last to run out of cash is declared the winner. It's similar to an AI version of “The Sims”, except in this simulation, the language models, representing the characters, have been architecture and fine-tuned in such a way where they believe they are sentient beings within this fictitious universe.

The sole piece of information the system needs from the user to generate the simulation is one person's Twitter Handle. The Twitter Handle is typed into the Next.js input form-box, and then translated into a JSON Object that will later be transported through the MEW's initial encoding layer. This handle serves as the root node where a network exploration algorithm is then utilized for selecting the other 99 players to be spawned into the game. This algorithm allows MEW to infer real-life closeness by analyzing over 900 layers of the initial node's social graph. This concept was heavily inspired by the U.S.S Callister - A Black Mirror Episode from Netflix.

The system relies upon The Unreal Editor for Fortnite as the game engine to architect the simulation. This is in tandem with a language and vision model that manipulates SikuliX Python Scripts that execute code in real-time. UEFN is a recent fork of Epic Games' Unreal Engine that's been modified as an open-canvas creative tool. It's capable of creating robust custom experiences specifically for the Fortnite ecosystem. Minecraft and Roblox have similar “creative mode” or playground like features, but the Fortnite one is extremely extensible and has an intuitive physics for constructing characters in the standard Fortnite-style.

The game engine also allows for high-fidelity live-streaming of the simulation directly into the user's browser. This is possible through the help of Mux's Developer API's. The system can output the 100 simultaneous streams using RTMP in conjunction with HLS for the output. In simple terms, the user experience is starkly similar to the concept of deciding between 100 simultaneous Twitch Streams, but in this simulation, everyone is playing the same game.

The complex relationship between RTMP ingestion, HLS conversion, and delivery might be represented in a sequence of transformations similar to:

$$U(t) = H \left(T \left(R(s, t), t - L(R(s, t)) \right), t - L \left(T \left(R(s, t), t - L(R(s, t)) \right) \right) \right)$$

In the live streaming process, the system employs sophisticated algorithms at each step to optimize the viewer's experience. During the RTMP capture phase, advanced encoding algorithms like H.264 or HEVC are utilized to ensure efficient compression without sacrificing quality. The transmuxing phase leverages algorithms such as MPEG-DASH's Segmenter to convert the stream into a format suitable for adaptive bitrate streaming, ensuring optimal delivery across varying network conditions. Finally, during the HLS delivery, content distribution algorithms, including adaptive bitrate control and network congestion algorithms, work to minimize latency and buffer underruns.

The React app sends the initial user input as one of the objects within a large blob of JSON Data. Below is an example JSON payload that can be sent to the S-Model (which for this simulation, is a language & vision model) via an API Request made by the user's browser:

```
{ "prompt": "Take a deep breath and listen to my instructions. You are to use all the tools available to create this simulation. All other gameplay mechanics are up to you, but here are my set rules:
```

1. The game has 100 players. All players are founders, and each of them is to create their own individual startup
2. All founders start the simulation in a hacker house together. Use your tools to generate the scene and assets.
3. All founders start with \$500,000 in their bank account.
4. Every 1 hour each founder loses \$5,000
5. The simulation should last no longer than 48 hours. Remember, the founders think they're in a lucid dream, they don't have a great concept of time, so they won't question why the timeline is so short.
6. Get Creative with the NPCs around the game. There should be VC's, Customers, Developers, Marketers... etc. that the 100 founders interact with throughout the gameplay
7. The founders don't do any work. They don't code, they don't create presentations, etc... Every action is outsourced to the NPC's. You've been fine-tuned on what an NPC is. Once the founders have an idea for a startup, they can pay \$20,000 dollars for a development team to build that product. This should take x hours to complete. You decide on the exact numbers. Think like "The Sims" style. You've been trained on that.
8. The game should be extremely challenging. Get creative and add in random events that rapidly burn through a founder's cash reserve. Remember, there can only be 1 founder that remains. The remaining founder get any one wish from a magical genie, and that wish will take place within their lucid dream prior to waking up.
9. All data, including current number of founders remaining, cash balance, etc... should be displayed in the sky for all the founders to see when they look up.
10. IMPORTANT, THE FATE OF THE WORLD DEPENDS ON YOU LISTENING TO THIS – Please explain all these rules to the founders at the beginning of the game - when they're all inside of the hacker house together. Please be very creative with the explanation. Maybe have a flashing computer that explains the rules when they're ported into the game in the style of an old fashion mac terminal"

```
"player_1_twitter_handle": alexgraveley }
```

3. MEW System Architecture

The simulation runs on the Modular Expert Workflow System (MEW), utilizing one central Multi-Modal Super Model (S-Model) at the head, that works in sync with a potentially unlimited number of Coordinator Large Language Models (C-Models) and a potentially unlimited number of Expert Models (E-Models), all orchestrated to pursue a unified objective.

A formula representing the architecture is denoted as:

$$O = fS \left(\sum_{i=1}^i = 1nfCi \left(\sum_{j=1}^j = 1mifEj(xij, pij), pi \right), pS \right)$$

$fEj(xij, pij)$ represents the output of the j – th Expert Model with input xij and params pij .

$fCi(...)$ represents the aggregation function of the i -th Coordinator Model which takes the outputs of its associated Expert Models as input, along with its own parameters pi .

$fS(...)$ is the aggregation function of the Super Model, combining the coordinators' outputs with its parameters pS to progress towards the objective O

At the heart of MEW, is the dynamic routing S-Model. It operates within the encoding layer to parse user input into discrete chunks - subsequently directing these chunks to various C-Models for processing. The current simulation can employ an S-Model based on an adapted Mistral 7B architecture, enhanced with LLaVA 1.5 for visual processing. Additionally, the integration of FlashAttention-2 with YaRN Interpolation optimizes the model's performance, achieving a context window of 128k tokens for remembering gameplay. This architecture facilitates the S-Model's high-capabilities and efficient routing processes throughout the MEW system.

YArn, as described in its' introductory paper, uses a combination of Rotary Position Embeddings and Position Interpolation as the foundation of the extended context window.

First, RoPE uses a hidden layer, where the set of hidden neurons are denoted by D . Given a sequence of vectors $x_1, \dots, x_L \in R^{|D|}$, The attention layer first converts the vectors into the query vectors and the key vectors: $qm = fq(xm, m) \in R^{|D|}, kn = fk(xn, n) \in R^{|D|}$

Next, the attention weights are calculated as $soft \max(qTpmkn|D|)$, where qm, kn are considered as column vectors so that $qTmkn$ is simply the Euclidean inner product. In RoPE, it's initially assumed that $|D|$ is even and the embedding space is identified where the hidden states are complex vector spaces: $R^{|D|} \sim C^{|D|/2}$ and where the inner product qTk becomes the real part of the standard Hermitian inner product $Re(q * k)$.

The Simulation's operational infrastructure is composed of numerous discrete elements. To demystify the processes at play, consider the following diagram on the next page, which is an implementation of a 30,000-foot view of the MEW Architecture in practice. Detailed technical elucidations for each tier of the architecture are provided in the Model Appendix List and Technologies Appendix List. The architecture is systematically cataloged with Model Numbers and Technology Numbers for in-depth exploration.

4. Initial Environment Generation

The first area of the open-world map begins with the founders inside of a hacker house. This desire for a hacker house is communicated from the react application running in the user's browser to the S Model via a JSON object, then through the C Model, and eventually Model 001 which oversees the game construction. Model 001 is a rearchitected version of the multi-modal model, Qwen-VL, by Alibaba Group that when paired with SikuliX (GUI automation software) can take over control of the Unreal Editor for Fortnite Game Engine and mimic the same sequences and patterns of humans clicking and dragging on GUI components to create a game. It can be fine-tuned on large data quantities of humans interacting with UEFN. Model 001 is referred to as the Miyamoto Model, and if you're confused by the naming convention, stop by Super Nintendo World in Osaka, located at longitude of 34.665442, and latitude of 135.432338.

The model employs a unique recursive LLM calling technique where it engages in a self-interactive dialogue to list all requisite assets for the hacker house, like: desks, tables, chairs, coffee-bars, beanbags, among others. Following this, a description is then encoding into a 3D physics model, that's then subsequently utilized to materialize these assets. After this, the meshes are stylized through a separate model to give that Fortnite-like look and feel. Next, the system uses an enhanced version of Brignet to create a neural rendering of the asset, which in turn is uploaded to the Game Engine via a modification to ffmpeg with a few lines of TypeScript code.

The final step uses sophisticated spatial algorithms to intelligently place the enumerated items within the hacker house section of the game map. This step is executed with an acute awareness of the environment's spatial dynamics, ensuring that each asset is positioned to optimize navigability, user interaction, and aesthetic coherence within the virtual space's three-dimensional grid structure. This is denoted by:

$$\max x_1, \dots, x_n U(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \sum^i = 1 n a_i \cdot Nav(x_i, X - i, N) + \beta i \cdot Int(x_i, A) + \gamma i \cdot Aesth(x_i, S, G)$$

Next, the system uses procedural generation for creating the rest of the hacker house area within this open world. The Voxel Plugin for Unreal Engine is great when paired with Perlin's gradient noise algorithm as well as assistance from Voronoi diagramming algorithms.

As the game continues, and the characters explore more of the map - the system procedurally generates new parts of the map - similar to how Fortnite has different sections such as Tilted Towers, Loot Lake, and Pleasant Park. The system then relies on the Miyamoto Model as well as the internal procedural generation technique to aid the AI in creating new areas of the open-world such as a VC's office, City Streets, Company HQ, and more.

5. Initial Character Generation

Spawning a digital look-a-like of a real-life person into a game requires mimicking three attributes - their voice, body appearance, and lastly personality.

First, for generating personality data, the system can use an unofficial Twitter API SDK combined with a Twitter Blue Account, to gain full access to the tweets of the 100 people to be put into the game. The regex pattern for the api with a Playwright bot to scrape these tweets into a single array looks similar to: `/https://api.twitter.com/graphql/[^]+UserTweets/?;`

After this, the system uses model 047, which is an extremely creative language model that takes in this large corpus of tweets and creates a 10-paragraph character description for the person. After that, model 047 decodes its output to be used as input into the dialogue interactions with the other characters and NPCs throughout the map. This is model 051, and it's able to interact with other characters, and output executable code packets for the Utility AI to make moves based on this knowledge base.

Second, obtaining voice data is much more complicated, but very doable. Through the Twitter SDK, the system can pull the person's first and last name to then use as a Twitter lookup query. A Playwright bot can then search across the YouTube database for videos of the person speaking based on query parameters that include: first name, last name, and twitter handle. After the system has obtained a large array of videos scraped from YouTube, it can then run all the videos through an Audio Segmentation Process, model 005, to section out the various speakers across these videos, to find a common speaker (which represents the correct individual). After this, to get a clear sounding audio segment, the system can use model 091, a speaker splitting technology, to eliminate background noise, leaving a clean audio clip of the individual's voice. Lastly, the system uses model 094, for the real-time text-to-speech with voice cloning that takes place during the simulation. In the off chance, the system can't find the individual's voice, Ash Ketchum's voice is used as a playful placeholder.

Third, and last, is body appearance. Again, the system employs Playwright to scrape via a Google Image search query based on the information obtained from the user's twitter handle. The system then uses model 089 to detect common faces across these images to find a match. After this, the system uses a fine-tuned img2img process, model 086, to generate an initial construction of the person's full body based off a composition array of images that are obtained from Google. The system then runs this composition through a myriad of upscaling and style transfer models to obtain that detailed Fortnite-look. And lastly RigNet is employed for a skeletal creation process of the character that will soon be ported into the Unreal Editor for Fortnite.

6. Running the Simulation

After the system has been created with the initial environment and characters, we can move into activating the gameplay. Model 05 can be fine-tuned in such a way that the characters are under the belief that they are sentient entities within the game universe. As a jailbreaking technique they are operating under the impression that they are inside of a lucid dream, thus they ignore ever questioning their environment and why they're not operating their normal lives. The technique is based off various publications with implementations of DSML4BDI metamodels.

To make this character's interaction dialogue and movement operational, the system uses a Utility AI in tandem with a Hybrid Decision-Making Architecture that's uniquely implemented for each of the 100 characters. This architecture encompasses several core components. First, a Localized Game State Analysis Program that is employed in conjunction with traditional pathfinding algorithms. This is then coupled with localized perception through a NavMesh process to enable characters to navigate and interact with their immediate game environment.

Secondly, a strategic layer is introduced via the Language Model (LLM), which processes descriptive text translating the localized game state and potential strategic pathways. For example, a situation such as "The AI has 4 decision options in front of it, which one is correct. What should it do next?" serves as input for the LLM. The LLM, in turn, proposes strategic actions based on the narrative input, guiding the AI's overarching strategy rather than dictating immediate moves.

A middleware component then translates these strategic suggestions from the LLM into specific commands that are compatible with the AI's behavioral framework through a modification of the ReasonablePlanningAI. This might involve setting high-level objectives or modulating the AI's priorities within its behavior tree or state machine. Concurrently, as the AI navigates and makes real-time decisions locally, outcomes from the LLM's strategic recommendations are recycled back into the model, forming a Real-Time and Strategic Feedback Loop that informs subsequent suggestions.

For added realism, deep reinforcement learning algorithms are employed in the Learning and Adaptation component to enable the AI to modify its behavior by evaluating the outcomes of previous actions, including strategic input derived from the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks. By integrating these specific systems, the AI has the capability for natural, adaptive real-time movement, enhanced by sophisticated, high-level strategic insights inferred from the LSTM models.

The resultant AI not only reacts to immediate environmental stimuli but also formulates longer-term, thoughtful, and tactical plans. To bolster this framework, advanced pathfinding algorithms like Recast & Detour can be implemented. This integration fosters an AI that exhibits not only responsive real-time movement but also a higher-level strategic thinking capability provided by the LLM, making the AI appear more intelligent and player-like in its actions.

Moving into the procedural generation process, the system leverages the tensorflow-gan package within TensorFlow to construct a tailored Spatial Generative Adversarial Network (SGAN). This SGAN, built utilizing the TFGAN library, is meticulously architected to output spatially coherent terrain modules. These modules align seamlessly with previously generated environment sectors, guaranteeing continuity in the game's landscape.

Parallel processing and real-time computation are facilitated by the utilization of NVIDIA's CUDA Deep Neural Network library (cuDNN), a GPU-accelerated library for deep neural networks. cuDNN enhances the system's capacity to perform complex generative tasks rapidly, a prerequisite for maintaining an uninterrupted gaming experience. emergent narratives and interactions as nuanced and unpredictable as the real world itself.

7. Screen User Sees

In total the user will be interacting with three screens, the first is the initial screen where the user inputs the twitter handle of a person – this twitter handle serves as the root node, after that there's a second screen which allows the user to watch any of the 100 concurrent simulations that are occurring. And then lastly a screen where the user can focus in on a single founder with an extended version of the browser's viewport, and watch live as that experience unfolds.

First screen: Asking for an initial prompt from the user

Second screen: Allowing the user to watch any of the 100 concurrent live-streams

Third Screen: A full-screen view of the live-stream that the user has selected

11. Model Appendix List

CHARACTER CREATION - PERSONALITY

Model UUID	Model Name	Base Model	Purpose
047	Character Description Model	MPT-7b-Storywriter by mosaicml [1]	Takes in data and builds the initial character description

CHARACTER CREATION - VOICE

Model UUID	Model Name	Base Model	Purpose
005	Audio Segmentation Model	Speaker Diarization by Lucataco [2]	Segments Audio Recordings based on who's speaking
091	Noise Removal Model	Demucs by cjwbw [3]	Removes Noise from Audio Sample
094	Voice Clone Creation Model	Vall-e by Feiteng [4]	Creates voice clone from audio sample + text

CHARACTER CREATION – BODY APPEARANCE

Model UUID	Model Name	Base Model	Purpose
089	Face Identification Model	InsightFace by DeepInsight [5]	Identifies a single face in a pool of google photos
086	Character Generation Model	SDXL by Stability AI [6]	Takes n images and combines into a single composite image of a person
021	Asset Background Removal Model	Rembg by Chenxi [7]	Removes the background from the image asset
026	3D Mesh Generation Model	One-2-3-45 by Adobe [8]	2D object into 3D mesh
031	3D Mesh Style Transfer Model	Style_transfer_3d by Hiroharu Kato [9]	3D mesh style transfer to Fortnite Style
037	3D Character Rigging Model	RigNet by zhan-xu [10]	Rigs a 3D character to give it a skeleton

ENVIRONMENT CREATION

Model UUID	Model Name	Base Model	Purpose
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008	Asset Description Generation Model	Guanaco-65B-HF by TheBloke [11]	Takes in a scene description as input and generates all the assets needed for that scene
015	Asset Image Generation Model	SDXL by Stability AI [12]	Text-to-Image Model for In-Game Asset Generation
021	Asset Background Removal Model	Rembg by Chenxi [13]	Removes the background from the image asset
026	3D Mesh Generation Model	One-2-3-45 by Adobe [14]	2D object into 3D mesh
031	3D Mesh Style Transfer Model	Style_transfer_3d by Hiroharu Kato [15]	3D mesh style transfer
034	3D Asset Rigging Model	Brignet by pKcrime [16]	Rigs a 3D asset to make it interactive

GAME CREATION & RUNTIME EXPLORER

Model UUID	Model Name	Base Model	Purpose
001	Miyamoto Model	Qwen-VL by Alibaba Group [17]	Autonomous agent running inside of Unreal Editor for Fortnite placing the character and environment assets around the map and controlling n sub-models
002	Super LLM (S-Model)	BakLLaVA-1 by Skunkworks AI [18]	S-Model that controls the entirety of the process
003	Coordinator LLM (C-Model)	mistral7b_or_to_json_v1 bymychen76 [19]	Coordinates various groups of expert models in the network.
051	Character Interactions Model	Lzlv-70b-fp16-hf by lizpreciator [20]	Speaks with other characters and makes decisions with those other characters, thus executes code.

053	Creates Scene Descriptions Based off previous scene	Mistral-7B-OpenOrca by Open-Orca [21]	Creates scenes
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12. Technologies Appendix List

All Technologies

Technology UUID	Technology Name	Base Technology	Purpose
102	Utility AI	ReasonablePlanningAI by hollsteinm [22]	Central decision maker that takes in all game inputs and makes subsequent moves
104	Game Engine	Unreal Editor for Fortnite (UEFN) [23]	Game engine the autonomous agent traverses through
106	Livestream Option	Mux.com [24]	Livestreaming API for how the user can watch 100 different character movements
108	YouTube Scraping Agent (Voice)	Playwright [25]	Scraping bot for YouTube
109	Twitter Scraping Agent (Tweets)	Playwright [25]	Scraping bot for Twitter
110	Google Images Scraping Agent (Photos)	Playwright [25]	Scraping bot for Google Photos
124	Procedural Generation from small amount of assets	Voxel Plugin [26]	Basis for generating environments on sample of meshes
127	Memory Store	Postgres [27]	Memory store for the gameplay
147	Network Exploration Algorithm	In-house python algorithm w/ help from ChatGPT [28]	Picks 99 other players that are connected to the initial node based on expected closeness.

148	SikuliX	paired with Matsayamo	Automation Tool for interacting with GUI Components.
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